

VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS ON PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION BASED ON CRAFT

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Key words: craftsmanship, national values, work skills, creativity, professional education, creative competencies, professional potential, professional-methodical maturity, professional skills, practical art.

Annotati on: In this article, the views of many of our thinkers and sages on vocational training based on the written and literary heritage of the development of national handicrafts in harmony with our spiritual heritage, the specific characteristics of national handicrafts, labor and vocational education, vocational training Information is given on the types of advice on choosing a profession.

ВЗГЛЯДЫ ВОСТОЧНЫХ МЫСЛИТЕЛЕЙ О ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ НА ОСНОВЕ РЕМЕСЛА

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Ключевые слова: ремесло, национальные ценности, трудовые навыки, творчество, профессиональное образование, творческие компетенции, профессиональный потенциал, профессионально-методическая зрелость, профессиональные навыки, практическое искусство.

Аннотация: В данной статье изложены взгляды многих наших мыслителей и мудрецов на профессиональное обучение, основанное на письменном и литературном наследии, на развитие национальных ремесел в гармонии с нашим духовным наследием, спецификой национальных ремесел, трудового и профессионального образования, профессиональная подготовка. Дана информация о видах консультаций по выбору профессии.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the practice of the world education system, there are trends related to preparing students for life situations by developing their technical and practical skills. In the field of education, attention is being paid to the formation and development of the personality of the student through the means of applied art, familiarization with universal values, appreciation of national values, and training processes that encourage culture and creativity. In recent years, in our country, thanks to the reforms to bring the education system to a new level of quality, starting from technology education, the need of students to acquire knowledge on the basics of science, spiritual and moral qualities based on the main national and universal values, work skills skills, creative thinking, and the normative basis for the formation of national crafts are being created.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Current modern vocational education in the field strategic of duties important directions designation for opportunities was created. "Craftsmanship more development and craftsmen on comprehensive support measures" [Uzbekistan Republic President 2017 year 17 in November "Craftsmanship more development and craftsmen each bilaterally support measures "about". No. PF-5242 decree: 1] in the decree of students spiritual perfect person being growing up them folk crafts and mentorship in instilling a sense of national spirit and pride of schools priority importance showing passed.

In the concept of developing the system of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, "formation of a healthy, strong and effective motivation to study in students from a young age and development of the ability to choose a profession, independently plan professional growth, and acquire modern professions" [Decree No. PF-5712 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030": 2] Scientifically based proposal on the identification of modern technologies for the implementation of the logical structural stages of the formation of creative creativity competencies in the process of teaching students to folk crafts, as well as the improvement of professional education by developing the primary mechanisms of national crafts among elementary school students in classroom and extracurricular conditions. and development of recommendations is important.

3. LIST OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In our country, A. Khojaev, R. Djuraev, U. Nishonaliev, N. Muslimov, O'. Tolipov, Sh. Sharipov, I. Choriev, N. Sayidakhmedov, Yu. Makhmudov, B. Muranov, A. Khojaboev , Scientists such as M.Shomirzaev have carried out research works dedicated to the interdisciplinary improvement of national crafts in the science of technology. The educational and educational foundations of the study of national crafts are covered in the research works of S. Bulatov, C. Hasanov, I. Karimov, Q. Kasimov, O. Khudoyorova, A. Turdialiev, D. Zohidova, O. Jamoliddinova. Training of future pedagogues, including various aspects of training of labor and vocational education specialists N. Shodiev, P. Magzumov, H. Rashidov, R. Mavlonova, U. Inoyatov, E. Turdikulov O. Ko' studied by ysinov and others .

From the scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), V. D. Zhukov, VIKachnev, AVYefanov, S. T. Tolstov, V. M. Masson, A. T. Trenozhkin, S. Rusakina, N. N. Baransky, G. Ye. Mupaveva, CPPucakina, N.C. Mironenko , NVKuzmina, N. C. Falkova, Yu. G. Lipes, A. G. Nizalievlar carried out research on the mechanisms of development of students' handicraft competences in the educational process, interdisciplinary improvement of national handicrafts, and some aspects of professional and creative abilities of the individual .

Foreign scientists such as D. Bell, D. Meadows, P. Kuusi, E. Toffler, J. Masudalar work on modernizing the content of technological education , forming technological competence, adapting it to social changes in society , G. Spencer , B. Blum, R. Mohanlar shed light on theories of creativity in education , development of professional competence of pedagogues , issues of competence, problems of professional-methodical maturity , formation and development of skills, skills and competences in the use of pedagogical software tools. worked

However, in the above-mentioned scientific researches, the problem of improving the vocational training of elementary school students by developing the primary mechanisms of national crafts was not specifically studied. This made it necessary to carry out scientific

research on the improvement of technologies with an integrative description of providing vocational training to students of the general secondary school through the primary mechanisms of national crafts.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

harmony with our spiritual heritage has been completed with great skill in the written and literary heritage of many of our thinkers, sages, and has become an eternal contribution to the cultural treasury of the world. The advantages of education and vocational training, the necessity of living with honest work in hadith, pandnama, narration, story, epic, proverb, ghazal, rubai, masnavi and other forms created in different socio-economic systems. [Shomirzaev MX The genesis of formation and development technology of Uzbek national crafts. Instructional manual. -T.: "New edition", 2016. -88 p. : 3]

In "Avesta" there are many such lines about working hard and making an honest living: "In order to create goodness and goodness, a person must work hard and create material blessings with his own hands" [Avesta . VI-IV centuries BC. - T: Science, 1963. -39 p. : 4] is noted. In addition, the following information can also be observed: " A person who does not work! Indeed, you will be among the beggars, bowing to foreign doors and bowing your head forever. "Avesta" is a large educational work in the form of a pandnoma.

Also, from the historical works, "Nightmare" consists of 44 chapters. It is watered by illuminating and analyzing other aspects of life. The 6th article entitled "About the advantage of the craft and the high value, being of a high nature" and the 43rd article called "About farming and market crafts" are for our research, that is, to encourage the young generation to work and learn a trade. It is extremely important for training. For example, verse 6 says: "O child, be aware that a person without skills is always useless and does not benefit anyone. If a person has a high lineage, original, but does not have a profession, if he is deprived of the honor and respect of the people, it will be worse than that" [Kaikovus. Nightmare. - T: Teacher, 1986. - 118 p. : 5] .

Both in this article and in the work, the same advice is given in various narrations and supported by real life examples. When it is said that "it will be useless, it will not benefit anyone", the author wants to protect the interests of the society, the people, the future first, and then the individual's own interests.

So, first of all, material or spiritual wealth is created for the society from mastering the craft, and the artisans themselves live comfortably and abstain from dirty work. "When it is said that the noble lineage is original, everyone, including the princes, should not limit themselves to their past, generation, and empty pride, and do not turn the face of this generation to the ground, only if you learn this skill, "If you don't engage in dirty work, only then will you save yourself, your family, your neighbors, but also your generation from all kinds of mockery."

In Farabi's works "Risola fi-t tanbih azret as-saodat" - "Treatise about the ways to achieve happiness", he describes in detail his dreams of a good, perfect, happy society. In his first work of the same name, he writes: "A virtuous society and a virtuous city will be such that every person of the population of this country is engaged in a profession. People will be truly free" [Abu Rayhan Beruni. Selected works. Volume 9. - T: Science, 1971 . - 663 p.: 6] .

In the work "Tadbiri Manozil" he urges all members of the society to benefit the people by engaging in farming, handicrafts, and animal husbandry. According to Ibn Sina, a life without work crushes a person physically and mentally. Explaining that such a life leads to bad consequences, he says that it is necessary for parents to educate their children about work from a

young age. In his opinion, a child should be taught a certain profession from a young age. Because after the child has mastered the profession to a certain extent, it is necessary to teach him from that time to use his profession, that is, to live an independent life with honest work [KIOtamirzayeva "Sharq thinkers' labor education" article "Scientific" magazine p. 310: 7] .

It is not difficult to learn from Abu Ali Ibn Sina's call to take into account the patient's gender, age, and strength as well as his profession when prescribing medicine. Also, Abu Ali ibn Sina paid special attention to the issue of the effect of professional activity on the human body, for example, he emphasizes that hard physical work accompanied by a lot of sweating hinders the work of the human excretory system. [DMAnvarova , PSergashev. Basics of career orientation and career choice. -T.: "Science and Technology", 2016.: 8]

Yusuf Khos Hajib's kindness to the artisans at that time was not by itself. For example, the peace and tranquility of the state, its position in the world, wealth, and the well-being of the people depended on this category of people. After all, vocational education was considered a unit of measurement of socio-political, material and cultural development. Yusuf Khos Hajib also expresses important thoughts about farmers, herdsmen, merchants, doctors, scientists, who have an important place in the development of society and the well-being of the people, and shows the place of each of them in society [Jalilova C . Kh., Khaidarov FI, Khalilova NI Professional psychology. - T: 2010. - p. 17. : 9] .

From our observations and analysis, it became clear that in educational activities in general secondary schools, in classroom and extracurricular activities, the spirit and meaning of nationalism in the forms of organization of productive work, the organization of folk crafts in local conditions, the methodology of preparation for organization has not been developed.

Higher education institutions are not adapted to improving the labor activity of students in folk crafts. Technology education classes in general secondary (special, vocational) schools are fundamentally different from other subjects (e.g., social sciences in the field of languages, physics, mathematics) with the following features: .

In our country, parents, teachers and school psychologists are of course very important in providing vocational education to students based on their existing abilities. Advice and recommendations of experts (psychologists, doctors, pedagogues, etc.) serve as one of the main factors to help in choosing a profession based on vocational training. There are several types of vocational counseling in different fields of vocational training, which differ from each other (Fig.

Figure 1. Advice on choosing a career in vocational education.

1. Informative tips. It is aimed at getting acquainted with the content of the profession as deeply as possible. It will introduce you to the requirements of the profession, where and how to learn this profession, employment opportunities. explains: in this advice itself, ways to improve your professional skills you can find out a lot of information about This is usually the case consultations are conducted by experienced professionals who have been working in the same profession for a long time.

2. Providing diagnostic professional advice . Based on the comprehensive study of a person, it is aimed at identifying and studying his interests, inclinations, abilities, and certain professionally important qualities of a person. The purpose of such counseling is to determine in advance in which field of activity you can work successfully, that is, in which field you can bring the maximum benefit to society and you will be satisfied with your work as much as possible [MF Ziyaeva "Interest in a profession and choosing a profession Journal of Vocational Education, 2001 No. 5, pp. 15-17: 10] Psychologists conduct diagnostic vocational counseling. They use various methods of personality research, such as filling out questionnaires and testing.

3. Medical profession advice. A person's health helps to determine the degree to which he meets the requirements of his chosen profession. If, for some reason, the profession you are aiming for is not suitable for your health, then the doctor will recommend another profession, that is, a profession that does not harm your interest and health. recommends to choose.

4. Correctional career advice. Such advice is necessary when teenagers choose a profession, but that profession does not correspond to their real capabilities and abilities. In such a situation, it becomes necessary to revise or clarify the professional plan. If there are elements of information-informative and correctional nature in medical professional advice, diagnostic professional advice contains elements of professional advice and so on.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Pedagogical conditions of the didactic system of development of creativity competences in providing professional education through national crafts in the general secondary education system were determined and justified.

By using various interactive methods "SWOT" analysis, "Holland" methodology, a broad approach structure of development of students' creativity competences was determined, professional direction was researched.

Levels of activity (level of acquaintance, level of recall, level of manifestation of skills and competences, level of creativity) were analyzed in the development of students' creative competences of national crafts in the science of technology. Based on the determination of the level of development, control tasks were developed.

- [1] Uzbekistan Republic President 2017 year 17 in November "Craftsmanship more development and craftsmen each bilaterally support measures "about". No. PF-5242 decree. www. lex. en.
- [2] Decree No. PF-5712 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" // People's word. –T: April 30, 2019. No. 88 (7318).
- [3] Shomirzaev MX The genesis of formation and development technology of Uzbek national crafts. Instructional manual. -T.: "New edition", 2016. -88 p.
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- [5] Kaikovus. Nightmare. - T: Teacher, 1986. - 118 p.
- [6] Abu Rayhan Beruni. Selected works. Volume 9. - T: Science, 1971 . - 663 p
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- [8] DMAнварова, PSergashev. Basics of career orientation and career choice. - T.: "Science and technology", 2016
- [9] Jalilova C. Kh., Khaidarov FI, Khalilova NI Professional psychology. - T: 2010. - p. 17.
- [10] MF Ziyaeva "Interest in a profession and choosing a profession" Journal of Vocational Education, No. 5, 2001, pp. 15-17: